

D4.4: Training Videos

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Revision History

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Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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Executive Summary

A main objective of the LoCloud project is to ease the task of small and medium-sized heritage organisations across Europe in making their contents accessible to Europeana. An important part of LoCloud's effort is to facilitate the process of taking local data from heterogeneous data sources and transforming it into Europeana compliant data. This process involves understanding and interpreting metadata profiles, extracting data, setting harvesting infrastructure, managing vocabularies, enriching/completing data, mapping metadata profiles and more.

LoCloud has several work packages devoted to the development of software tools and micro-services that aim to simplify the content contribution and ingestion process from the perspective of both content providers and Europeana. Throughout the project, time and resources has been dedicated to the development, improvement and testing prototypes of these tools, and working with content providers.

These video recordings have been made with the intention of helping LoCloud content providing partners and cultural heritage organisations to utilize the technology implemented in LoCloud. They aim to offer partners a quick and easy overview of all LoCloud offerings.

This report documents the recording of a series of training videos that present various tools and services developed and provided during the LoCloud project. The presenters in these videos are representatives of LoCloud project partners responsible for delivering project tools and services. The videos were recorded during a LoCloud training workshops, which took place in Poznań, Poland at the Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center's (PSNC) facilities. The recordings were made in PSNC's scientific television studio by professional PLATON TV¹ staff.

In total, 7 recordings were made with a total duration of almost 3 hours. These recordings were later processed. The final versions of the videos were published on the PLATON TV video portal, which delivers a professional video streaming service across various types of devices (incl. smartphones and tablets) and operating systems. In addition, these videos were embedded in LoCloud Support portal².

The videos can be viewed at: <http://support.locloud.eu/tiki-index.php?page=Training+Videos>.

In the near future these videos will be used to enrich the content of LoCloud's E-learning Courses, which are currently under development³.

¹ More information (in Polish): <http://tv.pionier.net.pl/aboutplaton>

² <http://support.locloud.eu/tiki-index.php?page=Training+Videos>

³ Preview version is available here: <http://support.locloud.eu/courses/>

1 Overview

This report documents the process of recording of a series of training videos, which present various tools and services developed and provided during the LoCloud project. It describes the final outcome of that process – a series of seven video materials with total duration of almost 3 hours. The aim of these video materials is to facilitate the use of LoCloud’s services by project partners and cultural heritage organisations by providing convenient way to understand the purpose of these services and how they can be used.

The presenters in these videos are representatives of LoCloud project partners responsible for delivering project tools and services. These videos were recorded during one of the LoCloud training workshops, which took place in Poznań, Poland at the Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center’s (PSNC) facilities. The recordings were made in PSNC’s scientific television studio by professional PLATON TV⁴ staff and later processed to remove any speakers’ mistakes and to add graphical titles, endings and subheadings (during the video), including proper marking of recording with LoCloud project logo and CIP ICT PSP funding information.

The second section of this report provides details on the video recording process, the third section provides conclusions and informs about the future use of recorded materials.

The report ends with an appendix containing more details on the content of recorded videos.

The videos can be viewed at: <http://support.locloud.eu/tiki-index.php?page=Training+Videos>.

⁴ More information (in Polish): <http://tv.pionier.net.pl/aboutplaton>

2 Video Recordings

The recording of the videos took place during the LoCloud training workshop in Poznań (20/21 November 2015). At that workshop all presenters were asked to deliver their tutorials twice: once for the attendees of the workshop, and then for a second time in PSNC television studio where they were recorded for the purpose of creating of on-line video training materials. Both presentation tracks were organised in parallel to minimise the time needed for these activities. The division of time slots in these two tracks is presented in Table 1 below.

DAY 1					
From	To	Training track	Speaker	Recording track	Speaker
09:00	09:20	Welcome, introduction to the workshop	Marcin Werla	<i>Setting up</i>	
09:20	10:45	LoCloud Collections - presentation	Marcin Werla	MORE	Dimitris Gavrilis
10:45	11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>			
11:00	12:00	LoCloud Collections - exercises	Marcin Werla		
12:00	12:15	Feedback/Discussion	Marcin Werla		
12:15	13:15	<i>Lunch</i>		LoCloud Collections	Marcin Werla
13:15	14:30	MORE - presentation	Dimitris Gavrilis		
14:30	14:45	<i>Coffee break</i>			
14:45	15:45	MORE - exercises	Stavros Angelis	Vocabulary Services	Walter Koch
15:45	16:00	Feedback/Discussion	Dimitris Gavrilis		
16:00	16:30	LoCloud Support Center	Runar Bergheim		
16:30	16:45	Summary	Marcin Werla		
DAY 2					
From	To	Training track	Speaker	Recording track	Speaker
09:00	10:00	MINT - presentation	Nasos Drosopoulos, Eleni Iskou	Geolocation Enrichment Service	Runar Bergheim
10:00	11:00	MINT - exercises	Nasos Drosopoulos, Eleni Iskou	LoCloud Support Center	
11:00	11:15	Feedback/Discussion	Nasos Drosopoulos, Eleni Iskou	Historic Place Names Service	Rimvydas Laužikas
11:15	11:30	<i>Coffee break</i>	<i>Coffee break</i>		
11:30	12:30	Geolocation Enrichment Service	Runar Bergheim	MINT	Nasos Drosopoulos
12:30	13:00	Historic Place Names Service	Rimvydas Laužikas		
13:00	14:00	<i>Lunch</i>			
14:00	14:45	Vocabulary Services	Walter Koch		
14:45	15:00	Summary, closing	Runar Bergheim		

Table 1. Schedule of trainings and recordings during LoCloud training workshop in Poznań.

The recording slots were significantly longer than the planned time of recordings to allow recorded presenters to repeat parts of their speeches if they were not happy with the results. Figures 1 and 2 below present the recording process of MINT training session. As can be seen, during the recording the speaker was standing in the TV studio, next to a TV screen.

Figure 1. Recording of MINT training session – TV studio view (21.11.2014)

Figure 2. Recording of MINT training session – control room view (21.11.2014)

The TV screen displayed the video signal from the computer on which the presented material (e.g. service website) was running. The presenter controlled the computer with a remote mouse and keyboard located on a table standing in front of the presenter. The same video signal from the computer was presented on another TV, not visible in the scene, but positioned to allow the presenter to see what he is actually doing on the computer.

During the recording there were three sources of video signal:

- Camera showing the presenter and the TV screen

- Camera showing just the presenter

- Video signal from the computer

These three signals were mixed during video post-processing to avoid typical “talking head” video and to produce something more than just a screencast. Because of that, the final effect are relatively lively videos which are pleasant to watch and help viewers to keep focus on what is being presented.

For the recordings speakers used materials prepared for the training workshops, but the recordings did not include the practical exercises that were also done during the training. It was decided that recording of practical exercises will not result in quality educational material and that recording these would distract training participants from their tasks. Repetitions of some sentences (needed in the context of recording) would have been practically impossible during real training.

Similar to the assumptions made for the training workshops (see LoCloud Deliverable 4.3⁵), the video recordings covered only those tools and services, which offer end-user interfaces and are designed for direct use by end-users. The LoCloud micro-services offering only APIs and which are integrated to the MORE service were covered during the trainings and recordings related to MORE.

The final outcome of the recording sessions are following 7 video materials:

- **LoCloud MORE Aggregator**
 - Speaker Dimitris Gavrilis
 - Affiliation Digital Curation Unit - IMIS, Athena Research Center, Greece
 - Duration 00:23:14
- **LoCloud Collections**
 - Speaker Marcin Werla
 - Affiliation Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center, Poland
 - Duration 00:38:27
- **LoCloud Vocabulary Services: Thesaurus Management Introduction**
 - Speaker Walter Koch
 - Affiliation AIT mbH, Austria
 - Duration 00:38:17
- **LoCloud Geocoding Application**
 - Speaker Stein Runar Bergheim
 - Affiliation Asplan Viak Internet, Norway
 - Duration 00:31:30
- **LoCloud Support Mechanisms**
 - Speaker Stein Runar Bergheim
 - Affiliation Asplan Viak Internet, Norway
 - Duration 00:09:18
- **LoCloud Historic Place Name Service**
 - Speaker Rimvydas Laužikas
 - Affiliation Vilnius University Faculty of Communication, Lithuania
 - Duration 00:15:33
- **LoCloud MINT Metadata Mapping Service**
 - Speaker Nasos Drosopoulos
 - Affiliation National Technical University of Athens, Greece
 - Duration 00:23:36

Appendix I: List and table of contents of recorded training videos to this deliverable contains tables of contents and single still shots of all recorded training videos.

⁵ <http://locloud.eu/Media/Files/Deliverables/D4.3-Regional-Training-Workshops>

3 Conclusions and Use of Videos

In this deliverable the process of recording of LoCloud training videos is described, as well as the result of this process, a **series of seven video materials presenting the practical outcomes (tools and services) of the LoCloud project.**

Final versions of videos were published in PLATON TV video portal, which delivers professional video streaming service across various types of devices (incl. smartphones and tablets) and operating systems. Furthermore these materials have been embedded in the LoCloud Support Portal and made available via a dedicated “*Training Videos*” page (see Figure 3 on the right): <http://support.locloud.eu/tiki-index.php?page=Training+Videos>.

Direct links to each video the PLATON TV player are displayed next to each on the dedicated “*Training Videos*” page in the Support portal. By using these links the videos can be embedded into any web page.

In this way, the recorded videos will be used to enrich the content of LoCloud E-learning Courses, which are currently under development.

These videos are also available for use by project partners to help them to promote tools and services offered by the LoCloud project.

Figure 3. LoCloud training videos embedded in the LoCloud Support Portal
(<http://support.locloud.eu/tiki-index.php?page=Training%20Videos>)

Appendix I: List and table of contents of recorded training videos

1. LoCloud MORE Aggregator

Speaker	Dimitris Gavrilis
Affiliation	Digital Curation Unit - IMIS, Athena Research Center, Greece
Duration	00:23:14
Link	http://tv.pionier.net.pl/_player?id=5092&layout=44&logopos=1&playertype=2&lang=en

Time	Subheading
02:05	MORE Interface Overview
04:35	Approach to Metadata Aggregation in MORE
08:40	Metadata Sources Setup
10:32	Metadata Harvesting
14:10	Metadata Ingestion
15:28	Metadata Transformation, Validation and Enrichment
21:50	Metadata Publishing, Withdrawal and Rejection

2. LoCloud Collections

Speaker	Marcin Werla
Affiliation	Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center, Poland
Duration	00:38:27
Link	http://tv.pionier.net.pl/_player?id=5093&layout=44&logopos=1&playertype=2&lang=en

Time	Subheading
00:24	LoCloud Collections Interface Overview
05:09	Creating New Collections System
09:59	Basic Configuration of a Collections System
18:18	Publishing Objects on-line
29:25	Creating Exhibits
33:14	Configuring Layout of a Collections System
36:13	Batch Data Upload
36:56	Summary and Support

3. LoCloud Vocabulary Services: Thesaurus Management Introduction

Speaker	Walter Koch
Affiliation	AIT mbH, Austria
Duration	00:38:17
Link	http://tv.pionier.net.pl/_player?id=5094&layout=44&logopos=1&playertype=2&lang=en

Time	Subheading
00:30	Theoretical Introduction
08:40	TemaTres System Overview
18:55	Practical Introduction to Thesaurus Management
29:00	Thesaurus Import/Export
33:58	Multilingual Vocabularies

4. LoCloud Geocoding Application

Speaker	Stein Runar Bergheim
Affiliation	Asplan Viak Internet, Norway
Duration	00:31:30
Link	http://tv.pionier.net.pl/_player?id=5090&layout=44&logopos=1&playertype=2&lang=en

Time	Subheading
00:20	Geocoding Application Overview
10:49	Geocoding Application Demonstration
15:07	Data Source Upload
18:32	Geocoding of Data Source Records
28:04	Geocoding Application Summary and Best Practices

5. LoCloud Support Mechanisms

Speaker	Stein Runar Bergheim
Affiliation	Asplan Viak Internet, Norway
Duration	00:09:18
Link	http://tv.pionier.net.pl/_player?id=5097&layout=44&logopos=1&playertype=2&lang=en

Time	Subheading
00:48	Support Overview
02:15	Documentation
04:22	Public Questions and Answers
05:57	Private Support Tickets
07:25	Accessing LoCloud Support Systems

6. LoCloud Historic Place Name Service

Speaker	Rimvydas Laužikas
Affiliation	Vilnius University Faculty of Communication, Lithuania
Duration	00:15:33
Link	http://tv.pionier.net.pl/_player?id=5096&layout=44&logopos=1&playertype=2&lang=en

Time	Subheading
01:48	Historical Place Name Service Introduction
03:07	Service Interface Overview
05:04	Example Use of Historical Place Name Service
07:16	Submission of New Single Records to Historical Place Name Service
11:00	Upload of New Datasets
12:45	Historical Place Name Web Service

7. LoCloud MINT Metadata Mapping Service

Speaker	Nasos Drosopoulos
Affiliation	National Technical University of Athens, Greece
Duration	00:23:36
Link	http://tv.pionier.net.pl/_player?id=5098&layout=44&logopos=1&playertype=2&lang=en

Time	Subheading
00:43	MINT Interface Overview
02:15	Importing a New Dataset
03:54	Working with Datasets
06:09	Metadata Mapping
21:32	Metadata Transformation and Publishing to MORE